

Pinagpala Publishing Services

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

VOL.V ISSUE X

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

October 2025
Monthly Issue
International

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269
DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433
TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183
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World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue X (October 2025), pp.32-34, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Voices from the Road: The Lived Experiences of Tricycle Drivers in a 3rd Class Component City of Negros Oriental

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Introduction

Tricycle driving is an essential source of livelihood for many people. Tricycles serve as one of the common and affordable forms of public transport in the Philippines, and millions of Filipinos rely on them for their daily activities (Tus et al., 2023). In the blue-collar sector, tricycle drivers are vital in the country's transport system, yet their experiences are seldom considered (Rosal et al., 2024).

Studies on transportation have found that varied passenger demands pose challenges to drivers, who, in turn, cut down earnings with the rising fuel and maintenance costs. Significant health risks had been associated with the job. Government requirements also pose an additional burden. The long work hours, competition, and sometimes moody passengers comprise their social and psychological struggles.

To date, there is a lack of localized publications focusing on tricycles as a transportation system. Empirical data tend to apply to metropolitan areas, which in turn, fail to capture the situation in a 3rd-class component city like Bais City. Guided by SDG 8, on Decent Work and Economic Growth, the researchers chose to pursue this study. The tricycle drivers and their families, passengers, the LGU, and NGOs were the identified beneficiaries of this study.

Research Questions

1. What are the challenges faced by tricycle drivers in Bais City?
2. How do tricycle drivers cope with the difficulties they encounter in their daily work?
3. In what way can the working conditions of the tricycle drivers be improved?

Methodology

This study utilized a phenomenological research design. This design places a strong emphasis on the subjective interpretation of life experiences and provides deep contextually-based insights by revealing the meanings people ascribe to their experiences. This study took place in Bais City, a 3rd class component city in the Province of Negros Oriental belonging to Region 18. The respondents of the study were the tricycle drivers with:

- a.) a work experience in driving a tricycle ranging between 5-10 years, and
- b.) a service route in Poblacion 1 and 2 of Bais City.

A total of eight respondents participated in the research. Data was gathered using a duly validated semi-structured interview guide. The interview guide consists of five key questions, presented in both English and Cebuano to ensure clarity and comfort for respondents. The data obtained through the interview was analyzed thematically using Braun and Clarke's method. Ethical clearance and the approval to conduct the study were obtained during the proposal defense.

Results and Discussion

Delving into the challenges faced by tricycle drivers, the ideas of rising fuel costs and inadequate daily income are seen in words like gasoline, earnings, affordable, and expenses. Few passengers on non-school days, unpredictable weather, and poor road conditions make the work as a tricycle driver even harder. Additionally, regulatory issues such as franchises, illegal operations, and permits add pressure, especially with unregistered competitors.

Economically, the ideas of savings and budgeting reflect how tricycle drivers spare an amount from their income and are cautious with their spending habits. Drivers also cope through prayer, a positive mindset, and a strong desire to succeed in life through their children, who are the primary reasons behind their hard work.

The tricycle drivers underscored "fare adjustment" and "income-augmenting opportunities" as ways to improve the working conditions. Price adjustment points to the minimum fare relative to the rising cost of commodities, while income-augmenting opportunities signaled the real need for more LGU and NGO-sponsored programs that can help the lives of tricycle drivers and their families.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Tricycle drivers in Bais City experience economic difficulties, which are aggravated by regulatory issues as well as environmental and social concerns. The multitude of challenges affects tricycle drivers means of livelihood and well-being. They are in dire need of livelihood programs and opportunities to improve their status in life. Despite these, the tricycle drivers have shown resilience through faith, positivity, and self-sacrifice.

As an output of the study, streamlining of regulatory processes, livelihood opportunities through micro-enterprises, and a public forum on transportation were recommended.

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Multidisciplinary

Journal

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DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17271404

